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WORK CULTURE MARKETING – A CASE OF VODAFONE LTD. BEHIND EVERY SUCCESSFUL COMPANY, THERE IS A SATISFIED EMPLOYEE-THE VODAFONE WAY

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ABSTRACT

Vodafone is an employee friendly organization and certainly worth quoting an example to MBA HR students. The illustration , shall help students, to get a practical insight about human retention strategies followed by Such big corporates.

This shall also relate to employee wellness and quality work life of manpower at workplace. The idea behind this is to, promote innovation in the field of HR.

Vodafone, India's second largest telecom service provider, has recently emerged the best telco to work for in the country in a study conducted by The Economic Times and Great Place to Work Institute.

Vodafone has implemented many such strategies in order to stand proactively in innovative work culture.

Key word : Vodafon is friendly organization at manpower conducted by The Economic Times The Vodafone Way.

7 new rules Vodafone's employees have to follow to avoid being fired (Source: Economic Times ET Bureau)

Vodafone India fired around 100's of employees who either drunk and drove or drove beyond speed limit or even without seat belt. They are officially reprimanded in this case and are terminated from job . Mr. Ashok Ramachandran told Economic times that he would rather have an EX LIVE employee then a dead present employee. Vodafone had recently came up with “ seven absolute safety rules’ for its employees. These rules also apply to personal life of employees.

(Source: Economic Times ET Bureau Dec 18, 2012, 10.06AM IST)

Historical Background of Vodafone

Vodafone India is a 100% subsidiary of Vodafone Group. It commenced operations in 1994 when its predecessor Hutchison Telecom acquired the cellular license for Mumbai. Brand Vodafone was launched in India in September 2007, after Vodafone Plc. acquired a majority stake in Hutchinson Essar in May 2007. From a single operation base with 31 million customers, the company has expanded its operations across the country to cover all 22 telecom circles and service 180 million customers. This journey is a strong testimony of Vodafone's commitment and success in a highly competitive scenario

At Vodafone India, the need to engage in responsible practices is led by an intense desire to contribute positively towards the three pillars of sustainability and CSR – Social, Economic and Environmental. The Mission, Vision and Values of the organisation clearly reflect its commitment, not only to the direct stakeholders but also to the society, in which it operates.

'Vodafone Cares' is the platform that ingrates all the good that Vodafone India does for the society. All the social initiatives undertaken are categorised under the three pillars of **Education, Empowerment and**

Environment(3Es) on which the 'Vodafone Cares' platform rests. These 3Es align the organisation's efforts towards being a socially responsible company and to make a meaningful difference to its employees, customers and the community at large.

Analysis of unique HR practices

Vodafone India is a employee friendly and cultured organization. With the unique strategies and innovation in HR practices Vodafone has been the aspiration of various job seekers. Nevertheless, these innovative practices have also been the reason of success of Vodafone in long run.

Organisation effectiveness and change

They employed around 86,400 people worldwide during 2012. Efficiency gains and related headcount reductions in Europe were partly offset by selective insourcing of customer call centres to improve customer experience, by acquisition of Bel Company in the Netherlands to strengthen the retail and distribution and due to growth in emerging markets. They are also continuing to move some transactional and back office activities to shared services centres in Hungary, Egypt and India.

Employment policies and employee relations

Their employment policies are developed to reflect local legal, cultural and employment requirements. They aim to be recognized as an employer of choice and therefore seek to maintain high standards and good

employee relations wherever Company operate.

Vodafone's goal is to create a working culture that is inclusive for all. They believe that having a diverse workforce helps to meet the different needs of our customers across the globe. An inclusive culture and environment is one which respects, values, celebrates and makes the most of the individual differences we each bring to Vodafone, to the benefit of our customers, employees, shareholders, business partners and the wider communities in which we operate.

They do not condone unfair treatment of any kind and offer equal opportunities in all aspects of employment and advancement regardless of race, nationality, gender, age, marital status, sexual orientation, disability, religious or political beliefs. This also applies to agency workers, the self-employed and contract workers who work for us. In their latest people survey, 88% of employees agreed that Vodafone treats people fairly, regardless of their gender, background, age or beliefs.

Health, safety and wellbeing

Vodafone has introduced a new safety plan to significantly reduce fatalities and create an injury free workplace. As a result they've seen a reduction in fatalities to zero in some of our countries (Turkey, the Democratic Republic of Congo and Mozambique). Sadly however, 21¹ people died in the course of Vodafone doing business around the world. Vehicle related incidents remain our number one cause of fatalities and we're addressing this through several interventions in local markets. **In Ghana, for example**, they have set up a programme that uses vehicle simulators to assess driver competence, and a weekly analysis of driving activities through a GPS tracking system to improve driver safety.

Employee Satisfaction unique strategy

Sunshine Wednesdays

Vodafone runs Sunshine or Watchful Wednesdays, which though not mandatory, are followed across most of their circles. All employees get to leave while the sun is still shining on the second and third Wednesdays of the month. It's meant to inculcate the habit of leaving work on time, so employees plan their work day better and have enough time in the evening to spend with family and friends.

"Employees appreciate the gesture and we have even had family members writing in to praise this special initiative," says a Vodafone spokesperson.

Performance, reward and recognition

Vodafone follows 3 R strategy for employee management.

Retain

Reward

Recognition

At Vodafone they reward employees based on their performance, potential and contribution to the success of the business. They benchmark roles regularly on a total compensation basis to support their aim to provide competitive and fair rates of pay and benefits in every country where they operate. They also offer competitive retirement and other benefit provisions which vary depending on conditions and practices in local markets.

Global short-term incentive plans are offered to a large percentage of employees and global long-term incentive plans are offered to our senior managers. Individual and company performance measures are attached to these plans which give employees the opportunity to achieve upside for exceptional performance as well as ensuring that as a business we do not reward failure.

An ownership mentality is a cornerstone of our reward strategy and senior executives are expected to build up and maintain a significant holding in Vodafone shares within a few years of joining the company. In addition, all UK employees are able to build up an ownership in shares through our Share save scheme and Share Incentive Plan.

Annexure 1.

Vodafone India: Leading Through Innovation And Collaboration (light reading india had an interview with HR head of Vodafone)

Source: http://www.lightreading.in/lightreadingindia/people-watching/156010/vodafone-india-leading-innovation-collaboration/page/2?utm_source=reference_article

Vodafone's Director of Human Resources, Ashok Ramchandran discusses the key HR challenges faced by the company, the role of HR in retaining top talent, and its efforts to make employees innovate and lead.

Light Reading India: How do you keep your employees motivated in the present uncertain times within the industry?

Ashok Ramchandran: We [at Vodafone India] provide opportunities to employees to upgrade their skills through robust organisation wide development interventions, job rotation, e-learning, individual employee education programs, so that they feel valued and proud being associated to a learning organization. The company recognises employees on an ongoing basis for their excellence in performance and for living the 'Vodafone Values'. Additionally, we keep people informed and keep them aware of what is happening in the company, immediate departments, industry, so that they feel respected and have the best information to make decisions and prepare themselves for their futures.

Light Reading India: What are the initiatives taken by Vodafone for leadership development?

Ashok Ramchandran: At Vodafone talent and leadership development is one of our key pillars of HR initiatives.

Our strategic ambition is to invest significant resource in these employees through various talent and leadership development activities.

Below are few examples: Senior Leadership Acceleration Series: This is 12 months development journey that focuses on individual assessment and development.

Leading in the Vodafone Way: Program designed to build awareness, internalize and operationalize the VIL mission and the Vodafone Way value system and becoming the Leaders of future for Vodafone.

Embedding a Coaching Culture: Programs designed and delivered for all people managers within the organization focusing to build the DNA for High Performance Culture.

Harvard Manage Mentor: Harvard Manage Mentor is an online learning and performance support resource that delivers high-impact enterprise learning for critical management and leadership needs. It is a single destination for comprehensive set of learning resources (from short videos to in-depth online tutorials) from Harvard Business School. It incorporates proven practices that reinforce learning and build skills. This powerful solution delivers on-demand performance support, enhances formal learning, and scales peer-to-peer learning.

Light Reading India: How do you see the role of HR evolving in the modern business environment? **Ashok Ramchandran:** We need to follow the approach of 'Think Global, Act Local'. The role of the Human Resource Manager is evolving with the change in competitive market environment. HR must play a more strategic role in the success of an organization by contributing to the strategy formulation process and being a strategic partner during the implementation of these strategies. The HR practices should be designed consistent with the strategies of the organization taking into consideration the essential HR needs. In order to succeed, HR must be a business driven function with a thorough understanding of the organizations big picture and be able to influence key decisions and policies.

With the changing Telecom scenario at Vodafone we are continuously focused on developing and designing organisation structures and processes that facilitate this change. And with our Customer First strategy we in HR is the employee sponsor and a change mentor for driving the strategy.

Light Reading India: What are the biggest HR issues faced by Vodafone?/

Ashok Ramchandran: For Vodafone India, continued focus on building strong careers for employees and building the next phase of succession plans are some of the biggest HR challenges.

Light Reading India: How critical is the role of internal and external communication for leadership development and employee morale?

Ashok Ramchandran: Communication is a major contributor towards organizational climate. Effective communication practices drive employee engagement, commitment, retention, and productivity, which, in turn translate into enhanced business performance.

Vodafone has an open environment which promotes easy accessibility of information. Information is shared on an on-going basis with employees through various formal and informal forums. We have regular town halls and pulse meets, as well as thematic surveys, apart from the Annual People Survey.

Light Reading India :What are the qualities you look for while hiring? \

Ashok Ramchandran: Our recruitment philosophy is to hire people with the right attitude and values that represent what we intrinsically stand for, all summed up in the Vodafone Way a common way of doing things and ensuring that we live up to the promise of providing better opportunities to our customers with speed, simplicity and trust.

We look for people who have the potential to grow into larger roles with adequate development, structured career experiences, and coaching/mentoring. In this context, temperament and attitude are very important as we believe that skills can be imparted and/or learnt on the job.

We have a high energy culture, and we look for quality of mind, drive and speed, ability to engage and change..qualities that make our leaders the successes that they are!

Light Reading India Is the role of technology and collaboration gaining prominence amongst companies? How are HR leaders taking help of technology to hire better people?

Ashok Ramchandran: Social media is becoming prominent influencing factor while hiring employees. The generation next and their comfort and adaptability with social media will be a critical deciding factor. A good part of our hiring comes from non-traditional forms and growing.

Light Reading India: Which initiatives are you really proud of and believe that they differentiate Vodafone from other telecom companies?

Ashok Ramchandran: We focus on 'Happy employees with great careers'. We are proud of our journey towards building a strong and differentiated and consistent performance culture. We have our Talent Management framework that identifies and grooms our talent for larger roles. Additionally, our strong investment in training and development, which helps our people succeed.

We believe in safety and our convictions to make it a culture which differentiates us from others.

Read more at: http://www.lightreading.in/lightreadingindia/people-watching/156010/vodafone-india-leading-innovation-collaboration/page/2?utm_source=reference_article

Annexure -2

7 new rules Vodafone's employees have to follow to avoid being fired (Source: Economic Times **ET Bureau Dec 18, 10.06AM IST**) http://articles.economictimes.indiatimes.com/2012-12-18/news/35890598_1_vodafone-india-employees-harish-salve

MUMBAI: If you are a Vodafone employee, using a mobile phone while driving will earn an official reprimand from your employer over and above the traffic ticket. Any more violations of a list of seven absolute rules drawn up by Vodafone and you could lose your job.

At last count, three Vodafone employees have been fired for drunken driving and 27 reprimanded for such violations of its 'Seven Absolute Safety Rules'. This apart, 37 employees of vendors have been barred from working for Vodafone and over 60 have been warned. Most such violations are at junior levels.

The seven rules address road and electrical safety and precautions while working in high buildings.

"This is now an integral part of our culture. We are happy to part ways with colleagues who simply don't get it!" says Ashok Ramchandran, director-human resources, Vodafone India, who spearheads the programme. "I'd rather have a live ex-colleague than a dead current-colleague."

This is part of [International Safety Rating System \(ISRS\)](#) that Vodafone is implementing across India as part of a larger global adherence.

In European countries, for example, state enforcement is sufficient. But in India, the company does adhoc citizen policing within the staff. Even the senior-most staffer is being watched by designated employees, said a mid-level Vodafone executive.

"A watchman once observed a senior staffer driving away without a seat belt and reported her," said an employee who requested not to be identified.

This code will apply not only to employees during office work/hours, but also to their personal

(Source: Economic Times ET Bureau Dec 18, 2012, 10.06AM IST)

<https://www.vodafone.com/content/sustainabilityreport/2015/index/operating-responsibly/health-and-safety.html>

Annexure 3

Interview of HR head Vodafone with The Economic Times

NEW DELHI: Vodafone, India's second largest telecom service provider, has recently emerged the best telco to work for in the country in a study conducted by The Economic Times and Great Place to Work Institute. Besides, a number of independent studies have also testified the same. In an interaction with ETTelecom's Danish Khan, Ashok Ramachandran , director- HR at Vodafone India, shares the journey to become the best Indian telco to work with. He also talks about the compensation policy along with initiatives taken to strengthen diversity and inclusion within its workplace. Edited excerpts:
Why do you think that Vodafone India is the best telecom company to work?

Vodafone India's journey to become "the best telecom company to work for in India" is built on a compelling employee proposition connects to our consumer brand. We encourage people from diverse backgrounds, industries and genders to apply to us and join us. This is boosted by creating an inclusive & collaborative working culture that encourages and supports speed, simplicity and trust for our employees and thus, ultimately resulting in a better overall experience for our customers. Our management focusses on providing employees exciting careers that help employees do exceptional work with exceptional people.

Do you think that Vodafone is at par with other telcos in terms of compensation in the Indian telecom industry?

In recent years, the telecom industry's focus has been on consolidation of customer base, enhancement of customer service levels, differentiation through brand experience and strengthening of the network to support the ever growing demand for data and voice. Given the macro-economic environment as well as hyper competitive nature of this industry, the market for the right talent has perennially been on the boil. That said, it has become pertinent for telecom operators today to be sharper in the way talent with the right skill sets are retained, rewarded and recognized.

Every year, a formal set of surveys helps voice the opinions of our employees with respect to their perception of the fairness of their total rewards, in comparison with what they note in the market.

As an outcome of these surveys, Vodafone has been running an initiative of "demystifying the Black Box" around Rewards. In keeping with the same, we have endeavoured to equip our 2,500 people / team Managers in understanding the science behind Rewards & Recognition, so that they may practice the art of retaining and developing their key Talent. All these initiatives boil down to our People experiencing objectivity and fairness.

Which initiatives you have taken that differentiate Vodafone from the other telecom companies? And, initiatives to strengthen diversity and inclusion within its workplace.

We focus on 'Happy employees with great careers'. We are proud of our journey towards building a strong and differentiated and consistent performance culture along with a Talent Management framework that identifies and grooms our talent for larger roles, and our strong investment in training and development - helping our people succeed.

Additionally, our belief in safety and our convictions to make it a culture is something we are proud of.

We believe in creating an environment that supports diversity and inclusion. To bring this belief in action, we started by targeting the core three areas which can make a difference that are creating and supporting careers, right communication, enabling environment & policies.

Vodafone has launched "Pathways to success" training program to enable women managers take charge of their own careers and to develop into leadership roles- 200+ women attendees in circle and corporate.

Apart from that, we introduced customized induction program and structured projects before giving them the role as soon as one becomes available. At Vodafone India, we give reciprocal mentoring for women talent on succession plans.

We also rolled out e-learning programmes on Diversity & Inclusion to create awareness. We have a maternity transitioning process for women / line managers and have policies framed for it.

Vodafone India has also formed prevention of sexual harassment committees.

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